

Approximations of inductor current for a fully on-chip Conventional Boost Converter in Discontinuous Conduction Mode

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Abstract—This work deals with design of a fully-integrated DC-DC voltage converter with topology of Conventional Boost Converter (CBC), where mathematical approximations for accurate estimation of timing constraints of power switches are addressed. Firstly, the time diagram of current flowing through the inductor is approximated by linear and exponential approximations, and then the dependence of switch-on times of power switches is calculated. Mutual deviation of these approximations is then evaluated and accuracy of each is determined. Exponential approximation is acknowledged as more suitable for fully-integrated design while the linear approximation can be accurate enough for a system using discrete components. Findings are confirmed by simulations of the developed fully-integrated boost converter that was designed in a standard 65-nm CMOS technology. The evaluated accuracy relates to the fully-integrated design in standard CMOS technologies, including an on-chip inductor operating in the discontinuous conduction mode (DCM). The performed analysis and presented findings might be very useful also in education, where curricula of different subjects on integrated circuit design can be complemented with accurate circuit modelling during the design phase. .

Index Terms—Voltage Converter, CBC, DCM, linear approximation, exponential approximation, integrated inductor

I. INTRODUCTION

Voltage converters are important part of Power Management Units (PMU) in today electronic devices. When the voltage value across a device needs to be adjusted to higher value, a switched converter is commonly used [1]. Design of switched converters is critical especially in low-power and portable devices or energy harvesting applications. To ensure minimized power dissipation, timing of the power switches in the converter must be accurate. To secure required accuracy for high efficiency of voltage conversion, one must understand operation of the converter in detail.

Conventional Boost Converter is one of the topologies commonly used in fully-integrated design [2]–[6], where accuracy of timing is even more critical. This paper presents mathematical description of the current flowing through the inductor of DC-DC voltage step-up CBC converter. The emphasis is on correct timing of the high-side power switch to minimize power dissipation when utilizing this switch as an ideal diode with zero threshold voltage. Reader should realize how mathematical approximation and neglect of real components (or parasitic effects) in such a "simple" and well-known topology can affect the overall performance.

II. CONVENTIONAL BOOST CONVERTER

Due to its nature, the Conventional Boost Converter [7], [8] shows many advantages important for the fully-integrated design compared to other topologies of inductive step-up voltage converters (i.e. Single-Ended Primary Inductor Converter (SEPIC) [8], 3-Level Boost Converter (3LBC) [9], Dual-Path Step-up Converter (DPUC) [7] or KY Converter (KYC) [7]). These advantages include using only one inductor (opposite to SEPIC) and only two power switches (opposite to 3LBC, DPUC and KYC) that is related to less intricate timing, and thus, resulting in simpler supporting circuitry.

Figure 1. Topology of Conventional Boost Converter (CBC)

Furthermore, CBC does not implement any flying capacitor (opposite to 3LBC, DPUC and KYC) that can increase power losses in the converter. CBC topology consists of two power switches (SW_{LS} SW_{HS}), one inductor (L), the output capacitor (C) and load (R). Resistor R_L is the series resistance of a non-ideal inductor. The CBC is shown in Figure 1.

III. TIMING OF POWER SWITCHES

For better understanding of the Conventional Boost Converter operation, it is essential to look into timing of power switches and time diagrams of corresponding voltages and currents. For this, we firstly divide one period of converter operation into three phases:

- **1. Phase** (Charging phase) - SW_{LS} is switched on (conducting), and SW_{HS} is switched off (non-conducting).
 - Current through inductor L and SW_{LS} power switch is increasing and voltage across inductor L is equal to V_{in} .
- **2. Phase** (Discharging phase) - SW_{LS} is switched off (non-conducting) and SW_{HS} is switched on (conducting).
 - Current through inductor L and SW_{HS} power switch is decreasing and voltage across inductor L is equal to difference between the input voltage V_{in} and the output voltage V_{out} .

The first two phases are occurring in converters operating in Continuous Conduction Mode (CCM) and Boundary Conduction Mode (BCM). The last phase only occurs when the converter operates in Discontinuous Conduction Mode (DCM), when the current through inductor drops to 0 and stays in this value for certain amount of time.

- **3. Phase** - both switches SW_{LS} and SW_{HS} are switched off (non-conducting).
 - Current through inductor L is equal to 0 and power for the load R is supplied from capacitor C.

Timing diagrams of the driving signals Φ_1 and Φ_2 for power switches SW_{LS} and SW_{HS} are shown in Figures 2(a) and 2(b), respectively. Both considered transistors are NMOS, switched-on by 1.5 V. Linear and exponential approximations of the current flowing through the inductor as well as voltage across it in DCM, are shown in Figures 2(c), 2(d), 2(e) and 2(f), respectively. Deeper mathematical explanation follows in the next parts of this paper. The explanation is concerning only DCM, where the CBC realized in the integrated form commonly operates because of low power conditions (μW - mW).

A. Linear approximation

Linear approximation of time diagram of current flowing through the inductor and other signals gives us simplified look on the operation of the voltage converter. Linear shape of the current in individual intervals is expressed as follows:

$$\frac{di_L(t)}{dt} = \frac{v_L(t)}{L} = \frac{V_{in}}{L} ; t \in \langle 0, t_1 \rangle, \quad (1)$$

$$\frac{di_L(t)}{dt} = \frac{v_L(t)}{L} = \frac{V_{in} - V_{out}}{L} ; t \in \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle, \quad (2)$$

where V_{in} is the input voltage, V_{out} is the output voltage of the converter and L is inductance of the inductor. After further adjustment, we get a linear approximation of the time dependence of the current flowing through the inductor of the CBC converter when charging and discharging:

$$i_L(t) = \frac{V_{in}}{L} t ; t \in \langle 0, t_1 \rangle, \quad (3)$$

$$i_L(t) = \frac{V_{in} - V_{out}}{L} (t - t_{onLS}) + I_{Lmax} ; t \in \langle t_1, t_2 \rangle. \quad (4)$$

The maximum value of the current through the inductor I_{Lmax} occurs at the end of the first phase at time $t_1 = t_{onLS}$. We calculate this value by substituting the closing time of the low-side switch SW_{LS} into the equation (3), which is also the initial value of the current for the discharge phase of the inductor.

$$i_L(t_1) = I_{Lmax, Lin} = \frac{V_{in}}{L} t_{onLS}. \quad (5)$$

In the DCM, the second phase ends at time $t_2 = t_{onLS} + t_{onHS}$ with the zero value of the current flowing through the inductor. Substituting this time into equation (4) and adjusting it, we get:

$$i_L(t_2) = \frac{V_{in} - V_{out}}{L} [(t_{onHS} + t_{onLS}) - t_{onLS}] + I_{Lmax} = 0,$$

$$i_L(t_2) = \frac{V_{in} - V_{out}}{L} t_{onHS} + I_{Lmax} = 0. \quad (6)$$

From this relationship, one can express the linear dependence of the switch-on time of the high-side switch $t_{onHS, Lin}$ on the switch-on time of the low-side switch t_{onLS} , and also on the input and output voltages of the converter.

$$\frac{V_{in}}{L} t_{onLS} = \frac{V_{out} - V_{in}}{L} t_{onHS},$$

$$t_{onHS, Lin} = \frac{V_{in}}{V_{out} - V_{in}} t_{onLS}. \quad (7)$$

This dependence is critical for the correct operation of the voltage converter. In order to ensure the condition of the accurate timing of the high-side switch SW_{HS} . Turning off the high-side switch when the value of the current flowing through the inductor is positive and as close to zero as possible, ensures that the direction of the current through the high-side switch SW_{HS} does not change, and the switch acts as an ideal diode with zero threshold voltage.

Figure 2. Timing diagrams of voltages and currents across inductor of CBC in DCM

B. Exponential approximation

In fact, the current through the inductor as a function of time takes the form of an exponential function. Exponential shape of the inductor current is dependent on series parasitic resistance of the inductor R_L and is more pronounced with the decrease of L/R ratio. When the series resistance is negligibly small compared to the inductance, the shape of time diagram of current flowing through the inductor is closer to the linear function. In other words, the charging (and discharging) time constant is longer, therefore it is more simple to operate in these time constraints without reaching inductor saturation condition.

The shape of the current flowing through the inductor in the charging and discharging phase can be described as follows:

$$i_L(t) = \frac{V_{in}}{R_{charging}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}} \right); t \in (0, t_1), \quad (8)$$

$$i_L(t) = \frac{V_{out} - V_{in}}{R_{discharging}} e^{-\frac{t}{\tau}}; t \in (t_1, t_2). \quad (9)$$

The time constants τ for both charging and discharging of the inductor depend on its inductance value, its series resistance R_L and the on-resistance of the power switches through which the current flows (R_{LS} , R_{HS}).

$$\tau_L = \frac{L}{R_{charging}} = \frac{L}{R_L + R_{LS}}; t \in (0, t_1), \quad (10)$$

$$\tau_H = \frac{L}{R_{discharging}} = \frac{L}{R_L + R_{HS}}; t \in (t_1, t_2). \quad (11)$$

The real time diagram of the current flowing through the inductor of the boost converter, without neglecting the

resistance of the switches in the on-state and the series resistance of the inductor, can be described as follows:

$$i_L(t) = \frac{V_{in}}{R_L + R_{LS}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t}{\tau_L}}\right); t \in (0, t_1), \quad (12)$$

$$i_L(t) = \left(\frac{V_{out} - V_{in}}{R_L + R_{HS}} + I_{Lmax}\right) e^{-\frac{(t+t_{onLS})}{\tau_H}} - \left(\frac{V_{out} - V_{in}}{R_L + R_{HS}}\right); t \in (t_1, t_2). \quad (13)$$

The maximum value of the current through the inductor I_{Lmax} during the charging phase is obtained by substituting the switch-on time t_{onLS} of the low-side switch SW_{LS} into equation (12).

$$i_L(t_1) = I_{Lmax,Exp} = \frac{V_{in}}{R_L + R_{LS}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t_{onLS}}{\tau_L}}\right). \quad (14)$$

By substituting equations (10), (11) and (14) into equation (13), we get equation (15), which in the DCM mode at time $t_2 = t_{onLS} + t_{onHS}$ must be equal to 0.

$$i_L(t_2) = \left[\frac{V_{out} - V_{in}}{R_L + R_{HS}} + \frac{V_{in}}{R_L + R_{LS}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t_{onLS}(R_L + R_{LS})}{L}}\right) \right] e^{-\frac{[(t_{onHS} + t_{onLS}) - t_{onLS}](R_L + R_{HS})}{L}} - \left(\frac{V_{out} - V_{in}}{R_L + R_{HS}}\right) = 0,$$

$$i_L(t_2) = \left[\frac{V_{out} - V_{in}}{R_L + R_{HS}} + \frac{V_{in}}{R_L + R_{LS}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t_{onLS}}{\tau_L}}\right) \right] e^{-\frac{t_{onHS}}{\tau_H}} - \left(\frac{V_{out} - V_{in}}{R_L + R_{HS}}\right) = 0. \quad (15)$$

By expressing the switch-on time of the high-side switch t_{onHS} from equation (15), we get the exponential dependence of the switch-on time of the high-side switch $t_{onHS,Exp}$ on the switch-on time of the low-side switch t_{onLS} , the on-resistance of switches (R_{LS} , R_{HS}) and the series resistance (R_L) and inductance (L) of the inductor and input and output voltages of the converter (V_{in} , V_{out}).

$$t_{onHS,Exp} = \left[-\frac{L}{R_L + R_{HS}} \right] \ln \left[\frac{\frac{V_{out} - V_{in}}{R_L + R_{HS}}}{\frac{V_{out} - V_{in}}{R_L + R_{HS}} + \frac{V_{in}}{R_L + R_{LS}} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t_{onLS}(R_L + R_{LS})}{L}}\right)} \right]. \quad (16)$$

IV. ACCURACY OF APPROXIMATIONS

A. Mutual deviation

Error of the maximum current flowing through inductor $I_{Lmax,Err}$ and error of switch-on time of high-side switch $t_{onHS,Err}$ between linear and exponential approximation depends on time constant τ of inductor charging and discharging, therefore it is dependent on components of the converter (inductance of inductor L , series resistance of inductor R_L , on-resistance of power switches R_{LS} and R_{HS}). Errors are also dependent on timing of the power switches and input V_{in} and output V_{out} voltages of the converter. These errors are expressed by equations (17) and (18).

$$I_{Lmax,Err} = \frac{I_{Lmax,Lin}}{I_{Lmax,Exp}} 100\% = \left| \left[1 - \frac{\frac{t_{onLS}}{\tau_L}}{1 - e^{-\frac{t_{onLS}}{\tau_L}}} \right] 100\% \right|, \quad (17)$$

$$t_{onHS,Err} = \frac{t_{onHS,Lin}}{t_{onHS,Exp}} 100\% =$$

$$= \left| \left\{ \frac{\frac{V_{in}}{V_{out} - V_{in}} \frac{t_{onLS}}{\tau_H}}{\ln \left[1 + \frac{V_{in}}{V_{out} - V_{in}} \frac{R_{HS} + R_L}{R_{LS} + R_L} \left(1 - e^{-\frac{t_{onLS}}{\tau_L}}\right) \right]} - 1 \right\} 100\% \right|. \quad (18)$$

For evaluation of derived expressions, the values of components used in manufactured prototype of CBC were used. The values are summarized in Table I. Figure 3 shows deviation of linear approximation from exponential approximation for values of the maximum inductor current I_{Lmax} ((5) and (14)) and switch-on time of high-side power switch t_{onHS} ((7) and (15)) within the dependence on the switch-on time of low-side power switch SW_{LS} as multiple of time constant of charging phase τ_L .

TABLE I. Values of components used for calculation of deviation of linear approximation from exponential approximation

V_{in}	0,5 V
V_{out}	1,5 V
L	11.61 nH
R_L	1,75 Ω
R_{LS}	0,5 Ω
R_{HS}	1,5 Ω

Even with the length of the charging phase comparable to the time constant τ , the deviation of the approximations of the maximum current I_{Lmax} represents approximately 58.2%. The deviation of the calculated duration of the discharging phase is 92.1%. At the length of the charging phase of 5τ , these deviations are 403.4% and 567.8%. The values of the time constant are chosen according to the exponential form of the current flowing through the inductor, according to which

at time 1τ , the current amplitude reaches a deviation of less than 36.79 % from its final value, and at time 5τ , it is less than 0.01 % from its final value [10] (applies to both charging and discharging of the inductor).

The results from accuracy comparison implies that it is appropriate to use the linear approximation for time duration of the first phase of the boost converter operation much smaller than the time constant τ of the designed circuit. Time constant τ depends on the inductance of the inductor and the resistance of the path through which the current flows ((10) and (11)). However, it follows from the values of the components in the fully integrated design that their ratio (time constant τ) is often in the range from ns to μ s [11]–[18]. Time constant of discrete inductors can be in the range from μ s to ms [19]–[21]. That means reaching condition $t_{onLS} \ll \tau$ is much easier either in discrete design or special RF technologies compared to a standard CMOS processes, where the linear approximation tends to be highly imprecise.

Figure 3. Error of linear approximation from exponential approximation of maximum current through inductor $I_{Lmax,Err}$ (17) and on-time for high-side power switch $t_{onHS,Err}$ (18)

B. Simulation results

Latter findings were also confirmed by simulations of designed CBC. In Figure 4, the comparison of dependence of switch-on time of high-side power switch SW_{HS} on switch-on time of low-side power switch SW_{LS} calculated by linear approximation (7) and exponential approximation (16) is shown. Third curve shows the same dependence obtained by simulation of schematic of designed voltage converter. Simulations were performed on scale of our interest ($t_{onLS} = 3 - 11$ ns) according to converter configuration and values of the device components. Duration of charging phase was limited by speed of the individual blocks of the converter's supporting circuitry and by saturation current of the inductor.

Important part of the whole designed converter is a fully on-chip inductor which was described and its properties and frequency characteristics were published in [22], [23].

Results obtained by exponential approximation shows higher accuracy to the simulated results with greatest deviation of 24.93 %. Results obtained by linear approximation are highly inaccurate with deviation over 287.45 % on the same

scale. Comparison confirms aggravated accuracy of linear approximation and suitability of exponential approximation for component values (mainly inductance L) used for designing fully-integrated voltage converters with topology of conventional boost converter.

Figure 4. Dependence of switch-on time of high-side switch SW_{HS} on switch-on time of low-side switch SW_{LS} calculated by linear approximation (7), exponential approximation (16) and by simulation

V. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we described shape of current flowing through the inductor in Conventional Boost Converter using linear and exponential approximations. Expressions (5) and (14) for the maximum current flowing through the inductor and (7) and (16) for switch-on time of high-side switch dependence on switch-on time of low-side switch were derived and presented. Especially the latter are important for utilizing high-side switch as ideal diode with zero threshold voltage and minimizing power losses caused by imperfect power transfer. Their mutual deviation was expressed and calculated for the values of components of designed fully-integrated voltage converter. The accuracy of analysis was confirmed by simulations of fully on-chip DC-DC boost converter implemented in a standard 65-nm CMOS technology. Results confirms higher accuracy of exponential approximation compared to linear one when inductance of the inductor is in the nH range, switch-on times of power switches is in the ns range and resistance of charging and discharging paths is in range of ones of Ω .

The performed analysis and presented findings might be very useful not only for design of functional fully integrated DC-DC voltage converter but also in education and teaching, where curricula of different subjects on integrated circuit design can be complemented with the emphasis on the importance of accurate modelling of the circuits during design phase.

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